

Crosslinking Process in Carbon-Polymer Composites

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ABSTRACT. Dielectric constant measurements on polyester-matrix composites of carbon black are reported. The samples were prepared by a curing process using a methyl-ethylketone peroxide. The variation of the dielectric constant as a function of frequency is analyzed for different temperatures and carbon-black concentrations. The results show a percolation threshold of a volumetric carbon concentration of 15.9%. The loss factor exhibits an absorption band about 100 Hz, which is not dependent on the carbon concentration. However, the characteristic frequency of the absorption band is decreased during the curing process, which can be explained by a transition of the effective dimensionality of the system due to the crosslinking process, *i.e.*, from 1-D into 2-D. The theoretical analysis is carried out using a collective vibrational model and the normal modes are calculated by means of a renormalization procedure.

I. INTRODUCTION

The addition of carbon black into polymeric materials has imparted many interesting and useful properties to the filled composites. In particular, the electrical properties of these composites have been investigated extensively in materials of high carbon content. It is well known that the introduction of conducting particles, such as carbon black, can substantially increase the electrical conductivity of polymers [1]. A sharp

increase in conductivity occurs above a critical concentration of carbon, *i.e.* percolation threshold. However, relatively less attention has been given to polymers of low-carbon content, where the basic insulating characteristics of the host material remain virtually unchanged by the incorporation of the filler. In this paper, we report the dielectric behaviour of polyester composites with a carbon-black concentration below the percolation threshold. The crosslinking process is investigated in detail and a vibrational model is proposed to explain the dielectric constant spectra.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The materials used in this study are a polyester resin with 50% styrene, from Reichhold Co., and a finely dispersed carbon-black powder, from Columbian Chemical. Some technical characteristics of these compounds are listed in the following table.

<i>Carbon Black</i>	
Particle Size (nm)	22
Nitrogen Surface Area (m ² /g)	110
Density (g/cm ³)	0.22
<i>Polyester Resin</i>	
Density (g/cm ³)	1.15
Viscosity (cps)	5000

Samples with different carbon-black concentrations were mixed in a vibration ball mill for three hours, and were cured at room

Figure 1: Dielectric spectra of polyester composites with different carbon-black concentration, measured at 25 °C.

temperature by using methyl-ethyl-ketone peroxide (MEKP) and cobalt naphenate. The samples were pressingly moulded between two parallel gold electrodes to ensure a good electrical contact and an homogeneous thickness. The measurement was performed by using a Du-Pond dielectric analyzer DEA-2970 from 25 °C to 65 °C. Likewise, changes in the dielectric spectrum during crosslinking process were also monitored.

III. RESULTS

The spectra of both permittivity (ϵ') and loss factor (ϵ'') are shown in Figures 1a and 1b, respectively, for the samples with volumetric carbon concentrations of 8.4%, 12.3%, and 15.0%. We can note firstly, that there is a clear absorption band near 100 Hz, which is independently of the carbon concentration. However, both ϵ' and ϵ'' increase with the carbon content. Finally, it is worth mentioning that the composites containing a carbon concentration more than 15.9% have a truly conductor behaviour, since in these composites the electrical charges can be transported through conducting particles by a percolation process [2].

On the other hand, the change of the dielectric spectrum for different temperatures was also studied and the results are shown in

Figure 2: Loss spectrum for the sample with a carbon concentration of 12.3% at four different temperatures.

Figure 2. It can be observed that the characteristic frequency of the absorption band increases with the temperature, and a second absorption peak appears near $10^{-2} Hz$ in the spectrum at 55 °C. This second peak is possibly due to dc conductivity [3], since the composites become conductors above 60 °C, the glass transition temperature.

Finally, the origin of the absorption band at 100 Hz was analyzed by looking at the behaviour of maximum loss during the curing process. In Figure 3, the loss spectra are shown for different times in the course of crosslinking process. It can be seen that the absorption-band shifts to a lower frequency ($\sim 100 Hz$) with time, which could be explained by means of a dimensionality-transition model.

IV. MODEL

It is well known that the molecular movements are responsible for the main relaxation of a polymeric solid [4], therefore, we can consider the solid as a vibrational network of molecules, which are bound by intermolecular interactions. The polymeric chains are typical one-dimensional systems and during the crosslinking process, the system becomes a high-dimensional one ($d > 1$), because the polyester chains are intercon-

Figure 3: Temporal evolution of the loss spectrum during the crosslinking process for a polyester composite with a carbon concentration of 12.3%, where the curing times $t_1 = 30$ min, $t_2 = 60$ min, and $t_3 = 240$ min.

nected by bridges containing from 1 to 23 styrene molecules, depending on the initial composition of the unhardened resin [5].

In order to estimate the effects of this transition of dimensionality, we start with a infinite square lattice, which is changed into a quasi-linear-chain by removing n vertical bonds in each $n + 1$ vertical bonds, as shown in Figure 4. We consider a simple central-force Born Hamiltonian, where the potential between two nearest-neighbor sites l and l' , when there are only small displacements u from the equilibrium positions, can be written

$$V_{l,l'} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha \{ [u(l) - u(l')] \cdot \hat{n}_{l,l'} \}^2, \quad (1)$$

where α is the strength of central force acting along the unit vector joining the sites $\hat{n}_{l,l'}$. The equation of motion for the Green's functions [6] are

$$M\omega^2 G_{\mu\mu'}(l, l', \omega) = \delta_{\mu\mu'} \delta(l, l') + \sum_{\mu''} \sum_{l''} \underline{D}_{\mu\mu''}(l, l'') G_{\mu''\mu'}(l'', l', \omega), \quad (2)$$

where \underline{D} is the dynamical matrix, whose elements contain the second derivatives of

Figure 4: Scheme showing the bond removal and the renormalization procedure. The circles represent real polymeric molecules, which are bound by an harmonic interaction. Likewise, the double circles indicate renormalized molecules at the end of the procedure and they are horizontally bound by an effective interaction.

Eq.(1) with respect to the Cartesian Components μ of the displacements, that is,

$$D_{\mu\mu'}(l, l') = \frac{\partial^2 V_{l,l'}}{\partial u_{\mu}(l) \partial u_{\mu'}(l')}. \quad (3)$$

For the case $n = 1$, the sites where their vertical bonds have been removed can be renormalized. Therefore, the effective central-force strength (α_1) between two second-neighbor sites is

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{\alpha^2}{M\omega^2 - 2\alpha}, \quad (4)$$

and the self-energies ($\epsilon = 2\alpha$) become

$$\epsilon = 2\alpha + \frac{2\alpha^2}{M\omega^2 - 2\alpha} = 2\alpha + 2\alpha_1. \quad (5)$$

In this way, the original square lattice has become a rectangular one, since the horizontal interactions are different from the vertical ones. This renormalization procedure, which was first introduced by Barrio and Benitez [7], can be performed for every n . When $n \rightarrow \infty$, the lattice will reduce to be a quasi-one-dimension case. The vibrational density

Figure 5: Phonon density of states (DOS) from a infinite square lattice with both $n = 0$ and $n = 50$, according to Fig. 4. A small imaginary part (of the order of 10^{-2} times the band width) has been added to the frequency and $\omega_{max} = (8\alpha/M)^{1/2}$.

of states (DOS), which can be calculated by using the Green's functions, is given by [8]

$$\rho(\omega) = -\frac{2\omega}{\pi} \text{Im}\{\text{Tr}G(\omega)\}. \quad (6)$$

Taking advantage of the translational symmetries of the rectangular lattice, the numerical calculation was carried out in the reciprocal space. The DOS for both $n = 0$ and $n = 50$ are shown in Figures 5a and 5b, respectively. Notice that there is a shift to lower frequency of the maximum during the dimensionality transition from 1D (Fig. 5b) to 2D (Fig. 5a), in agreement with the experimental results. It is worth mentioning that for a real linear chain, there is a finite DOS at $\omega = 0$ due to the van Hove singularity [8], and $\omega_{max}(1D) = \sqrt{4\alpha/M}$. However, these aspects do not appear in Fig. 5b, since in the case of $n = 50$ the system is not a truly linear chain and "remembers" some of its two-dimensional characteristics.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have reported dielectric constant measurements on polyester composites based on carbon black. The variation of dielectric

spectra has been analyzed for different temperatures and carbon-black concentrations. As a conclusion we can state that there is a percolation threshold of volumetric carbon concentration of 15.9% and a glass transition temperature at about 60°C in these composites. Likewise, there is an absorption band at 100 Hz in the loss factor spectra, which is independent of the carbon concentration. However, the characteristic frequency of this absorption band decreases during the curing process, which is qualitatively explained by a transition of the effective dimensionality, from 1D into 2D, of the system due to the crosslinking process.

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